

The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support and Work-Life Balance on Employee Engagement Mediated by Job Satisfaction at PT Rekayasa Industri

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Abstract:- Employee engagement is considered necessary for an organization because it helps create a better work culture, increases productivity, and impacts company profits. This study aims to determine the effect of perceived organizational support and work-life balance on employee engagement mediated by job satisfaction at PT Rekayasa Industri, with a total sample of 120 employees. The data analysis method used Structural Equation Model-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS). The results of this study indicate that perceived organizational support and work-life balance have a positive and significant effect on employee engagement mediated by job satisfaction. Work-life balance and job satisfaction have a positive and significant impact on employee engagement directly. Perceived organizational support does not have a substantial direct effect on employee engagement but has a positive and significant impact with perfect mediation through job satisfaction. The implications of this research are discussed in the article.

Keywords:- Employee Engagement, Job Satisfaction, Perceived Organizational Support, Work-Life Balance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Companies must have a strategy while dealing with the business world, where competition is fiercer. Organizations must effectively carry out organizational goals in light of rapid and sophisticated development. As a result, the organization itself needs the contribution of human resources. The company's human resources are a valuable resource. Good human resources will enable the organization to mobilize other resources that will help it advance and grow so that it can endure in the face of fierce commercial competition. Consequently, effective human resource management is crucial to achieving corporate goals.

PT Engineering Industry, commonly referred to as Rekind, is a subsidiary of a State-Owned Enterprise (BUMN) engaged in the EPC (Engineering, Procurement, and Construction) sector. Since its inception on August 12, 1981, Rekind has been determined to realize industrial independence in the country by developing the engineering and design business for large-scale projects in the fields of Energy, Minerals, and Chemicals. In developing its business, Rekind requires human resources who have a sense of job satisfaction and a sense of involvement with the company.

The degree of happiness a person experiences at work is known as job satisfaction. Various workplace circumstances in their workplace adequately compensate for the degree of personal fulfillment they experience. Job satisfaction is related to employee psychology within an organization, which is influenced by the environment's perceived events [1]. Employees who are very satisfied with their jobs are more likely to be dedicated, engaged, and contribute to the firm. As a result, they are more likely to want to put in extra effort and be more productive. In contrast, under-satisfied workers are more likely to leave their jobs, exhibit poorer work habits, and produce less [2].

Based on the results of interviews conducted by the leaders of the Remuneration and Industrial Relations (RIR) Division of PT Rekayasa Industri, the Perceived Organizational Support (POS) variable is suspected to affect employee engagement, considering the result of a decrease in the percentage of index satisfaction "acknowledge" or a sense of recognition and appreciation from the company is quite high. In addition, the variable work-life balance can also be used for this study with the condition of companies implementing the Work From Anywhere (WFA) system to determine its effect on employee engagement which is mediated by job satisfaction.

When an employee feels valued by their employer and cared for, this is known as perceived organizational support or POS [3]. This is also in line with the opinion that states that one of the antecedents of employees being able to reach engaged levels is perceived organizational support (POS). POS is believed to be essential for engagement between employees and companies where he works [4].

Employee engagement is not the only factor influencing job satisfaction and employee engagement; the work-life balance, or WLB, is another important one. Job-life ratio refers to a person's ability to adapt to various interests and activities in his work, home, and personal life while maintaining a suitable degree of involvement or "fit" between multiple positions in his life [5]. According to another study, work-life balance refers to how closely people feel connected to and content with their work- and family life and how well they can handle both demands [6].

The researcher conducted a pre-survey which has results on the four variables that have been carried out; it can be said that PT Engineering Industrial employees still feel a lack of perceptions of company support (POS), the balance between work and personal life (Work-Life Balance), job satisfaction, and a sense of being engaged with the company (employee engagement). This is reinforced by the employee turnover data obtained from the results of interviews with the leaders of the Remuneration and Industrial Relations (RIR) Division of PT Rekayasa Industry during the last two years, namely 2020 – 2021; there was a significant increase in the employee turnover rate which shows the number of employees resigning 29 employees with a turnover rate of 3% in 2020 and experienced a surge in the number of employees leaving by 88 employees with a turnover percentage of 10% in 2021. The increase in the number of employees resigning from 2020 and 2021 is quite significant; a sense of dissatisfaction with employees at work can cause a jump in this turnover rate.

Two different conclusions were drawn from prior research on the impact of perceived organizational support (POS) on employee engagement. According to study findings, perceived organizational support (POS) significantly boosts employee engagement [7], [8].

However, according to the findings of another study, employee engagement is unaffected by perceived organizational support [9]. This is also consistent with research findings that POS has little to no beneficial impact on employee engagement [10]. This study will examine the effects of work-life balance on employee engagement and the impact of perceived organizational support. According to findings from a prior study, employee engagement is significantly boosted by work-life balance [11]. Similar research findings indicated that employee commitment or engagement increased with a more substantial work-life balance [12]. According to the results of a different study, work-life balance does not influence employee engagement other than a strongly favorable effect. Therefore, the less impact it will have on the employee, the stronger the work-life balance [13].

Based on these issues, this article seeks to: (1) identify and analyze the relationship between perceived organizational support and job satisfaction; (2) understand and analyze the relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction; (3) understand and analyze the relationship between perceived organizational support and employee engagement; (4) understand and analyze the relationship between job satisfaction and employee engagement; (5) understand and analyze the relationship between job satisfaction and employee engagement; (6) knowing and analyzing job satisfaction mediating the effect of perceived organizational support on employee engagement; and (7) knowing and analyzing job satisfaction mediates the effect of work-life balance on employee engagement.

II. THEORETICAL REVIEW

A. Definition of Perceived Organizational Support

Perceived Organizational Support (POS) is a form of support that comes not only from the organization, but also from superiors and colleagues. Perceived Organizational Support is also the ability to show and employ oneself without negative consequences, where supportive and trusting interpersonal relationships and supportive management will increase psychological security [7]. Increased perceived organizational support will make employees feel obligated to contribute and care about the organization's welfare and help it achieve its goals [14]. Workers feel secure when there is open communication and organizational support [8]. Members can experiment, try new things, and even fail without fear of repercussions in a friendly environment.

Employees will perceive their work as a reciprocal relationship reflecting relative dependence, meaning that they and the organization are involved in reciprocity [15]. Therefore, organizational support is how businesses or organizations recognize employee contributions to the advancement of the firm or the organization and the concern for their well-being (care about employee well-being) [9]

Some factors influence perceived organizational support as follows; (1) trust, (2) access to information, (3) access to opportunities to learn and develop. At the same time, aspects of perceived organizational support are (1) appreciation of employee contributions, and (2) attention and concern for employee welfare.

B. Work-Life Balance

The concept of work-life balance describes how people balance their relationships with their families, professional lives, and home environments [15]. According to this notion, although "work" and "family" are based in various settings or domains, they might impact one another. Right away, it is critical to recognize that achieving a work-life balance does not include spending the same amount of time in each role [16]. However, a more extensive definition of work-life balance consists of the degree of happiness with foreign involvement in different positions.

Work-life balance is typically referred to as a balance point or effort to keep people's m in life in harmony [17]. According to some studies, work-life balance is a state in which people experience less tension and can successfully balance their roles in work and family [18]. Workplace practices that claim to support employees' requirements in striking a balance between the demands of family and professional life are known as work-life balance practices. Based on the numerous definitions currently in use, work-life balance is a condition of equilibrium caused by a bit of conflict between demands on one's life and those of one's family so that the various functions can run together.

There are four main factors for achieving work-life balance, namely as follows: (1) individual factors, (2) organizational factors, (3) societal factors, and other factors.

C. Job Satisfaction

A worker's attitude toward their job is influenced by work-related conditions, employee cooperation, benefits gained at work, and issues linked to physical and psychological elements [19]. A positive or negative emotional state and how employees evaluate their work are indicators of job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is influenced by turnover, absenteeism, age, job levels, and company organizational size [20].

Job satisfaction is influenced by factors like turnover, absence rates, age, job levels, and the organizational scale of the company [20]. High work satisfaction is always correlated with low turnover and vice versa; if many employees are unsatisfied, then staff turnover is high. Because employees in a company are the primary determinant of whether organizational operations are successful or unsuccessful, job happiness is crucial [21]. Job satisfaction is a personal matter because each person will express varying levels of joyous depending on the circumstances [22].

From the justifications above, it can be inferred that employees' feelings towards the pleasant or unpleasant aspects

of their work constitute job satisfaction. Piece tied to motivation produces job satisfaction. It depends on how the person perceives the suitability or conflict between their goals and the result that determines whether or not they are content or unsatisfied with their work.

Several factors influence job satisfaction 1) opportunity to advance, 2) communication, and 3) facilities.

D. Employee Engagement

Employee Engagement is the emotional feelings employees have for the organization and the actions they take to ensure the organization is successful; employees who are already attached to the company show concern, dedication, passion, accountability, and focus on results [23]. Employee involvement, personal involvement, satisfaction, and excitement for their work are further definitions of employee engagement [24]. Employees' access to tools and opportunities to gain new skills, their perception of the importance and significance of their work, and the emphasis placed on their connections with co-workers are all things we might inquire about.

Fig 1. HYPOTHESIS
SOURCE: PERSONAL DOCUMENTATION, 2022

E. Hypothesis

- H1: Perceived organizational support has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction
- H2: Work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction
- H3: Perceived organizational support has a positive and significant effect on employee engagement
- H4: Work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on employee engagement
- H5: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee engagement

Employee engagement shows how much employees identify with their work, are emotionally committed to it, and have the abilities and resources to do the job [23]. Another statement strengthens that employee engagement is a level of

commitment and involvement from an employee, a sense of belonging to the organization, and commitment to maintaining organizational values [25]. Based on some of the viewpoints above of the experts, it can be deduced that employee engagement is the attitude of employees in a company who can act beyond what the company asks of them and who is full of caring, dedication, passion, accountability, and focus as well as achieving employee engagement, individual involvement, satisfaction, and enthusiasm for the work they do.

There are three levels of engagement with employees: engaged, not engaged, and actively disengaged. Furthermore, three factors influence employee engagement: job resources, the salience of job resources, and personal resources. This study's dimensions of employee engagement are vigor, dedication, and absorption.

H6: Perceived organizational support has a positive and significant effect on employee engagement through job satisfaction

H7: Work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on employee engagement in job satisfaction

I. METHODOLOGY

This type of study will employ a descriptive/explanatory research method with a quantitative approach. 120 HO workers from the PT Engineering Industry who had been used for more than five years served as the study's samples. The demographic information about each respondent, such as gender, age, final educational attainment, and years of service, was used to describe their personalities. Work-life balance and perceived organizational support (POS) (X1) are the study's independent variables (X2). Employee involvement is the study's dependent variable (Y2). Job satisfaction is the interviewing factor (Y1). A Likert scale was utilized as the measurement tool for this study, with the following criteria: 5 = highly agree, 4 = good, 3 = good enough, 2 = not good, and 1 = extremely bad.

The distribution of questionnaires, observation, and documentation were the methods used in this study's data gathering. Purposive random sampling was used to acquire data from the respondents. Structural equation modeling (SEM) with the partial least squares (PLS) approach was utilized to analyze the data for this study.

II. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Descriptive Analysis

Analysis descriptive gives information about the minimum value, value maximum, and average value or means from answer respondents on variables study that is Perceived Organizational Support (X1), Work-Life Balance (X2), Satisfaction Work (Y1), and Employee Engagement (Y2). Calculation results analysis descriptive will be described as each following.

1) Variable Descriptive Analysis of Perceived Organizational Support (X1)

Analysis results from descriptive showing score explanatory variable Perceived Organizational Support (POS) with a minimum value of 3.25 and value maximum of 3.83. The average value of the POS variable is 3.56. Based on the average value, scores are in numbers 3 and 4, p this showing that respondents do not agree enough to agree with the response statement on the POS variable.

2) Variable Descriptive Analysis of Work-Life Balance (X2)

Analysis results show a score descriptive variable work-life balance (WLB) with 3.10 as the minimum value and 4.04 as the maximum. Based on the average value, the WLB variable is 3.77. Based on the average value, scores are in numbers 3 and 4, p this showing that respondents have a level of agreement in the response statement on the WLB variable.

3) Variable Descriptive Analysis of Job Satisfaction (Y1)

Analysis results show the descriptive value of the job satisfaction variable with 3.18 as the least and 4.10 as the maximum. Based on the average value, the job satisfaction variable is 3.61. Based on this average value, it can be seen that the value is in numbers 3 and 4; this shows that respondents have a level of agreement in response to statements on the Job Satisfaction variable.

4) Descriptive Analysis of Employee Engagement (Y2)

The analysis's findings demonstrate that the descriptive value of the employee engagement variable has 3.58 as the most negligible value and 4.03 as the maximum. Based on the average value, the employee engagement variable is 3.74. Based on this average value, it can be seen that the values are in numbers 3 and 4; this shows that respondents have a level of agreement in responding to statements on the employee engagement variable.

B. Hypothesis Test Results

The following is presented in the discussion of the hypothesis based on the statistical result findings regarding the impact of the direct and indirect relationships, which are depicted in table 1:

1) Hypothesis 1 - The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Job Satisfaction

Table 1 yields a t statistic value of 10.123, which is higher than the value in the t table, which is 1.980, and a P-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. According to this, H_a is accepted since the POS variable has a favorable and significant impact on job satisfaction. The sensed corporate support variable has a 65.5% positive and more substantial impact on job satisfaction, according to the path coefficient value of 0.655. Because t statistics $>$ t table or P-values $<$ 0.05, the study's H_1 is accepted, which claims that "Perceived organizational support has a positive and substantial effect on job satisfaction."

2) Hypothesis 2 – Effect of Work-Life Balance on Job Satisfaction

Table 1 yields a t statistic value of 2.993, which is higher than the value in the t table, which is 1.980, and a P-value of 0.003, which is lower than 0.05. This claims that H_a is accepted because the work-life balance variable has a favorable and significant impact on job satisfaction. The work-life balance variable has a positive and substantial effect on job satisfaction by 28.8%, according to the path coefficient value of 0.228. Because t statistic $>$ t table or P-values $<$ 0.05, the study's H_2 , which claims that "Work life balance has a positive and substantial effect on job satisfaction," is accepted.

3) Hypothesis 3 – The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Employee Engagement

Table 1 shows a t-statistic value of 0.369, less than the t-table t -table 1.980, and a P-value of 0.712, higher than 0.05, obtained. This means that H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected, i.e., the perceived organizational support variable does not affect employee engagement roles. Because the t statistic t table or P-values $>$ 0.05, the H_3 hypothesis in this study, which

asserts that "Perceived organizational support has an influence and is significant on employee engagement," is rejected. This indicates that employee engagement outcomes are unaffected by how strongly employees perceive their employer's support (POS).

4) Hypothesis 4 – Effect of Work-Life Balance on Employee Engagement

Based on Table 1, the P-value is 0.024, less than 0.05, and the t-statistic value is 2.257, which is higher than the t-table

value of 1.980. According to this, Ha is acknowledged since the work-life balance variable has a favorable and substantial impact on employee engagement. The work-life balance variable has a 20.6% positive and significant effect on employee engagement, according to the path coefficient value of 0.206. Because t statistic > t table or P-values < 0.05, it is recognized that H4 in this study, which indicates that "Work life balance has a positive and substantial effect on employee engagement," is accepted.

FIG 2. INITIAL SCORE OF LOADING FACTOR
 SOURCE: ANALYZE WITH SMARTPLS, 2022

Connection Between Construct	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Desc.
Direct effect				
Perceived Organizational Support -> Satisfaction Work	0.655	10.123	0.000	accepted
Work-Life Balance -> Satisfaction Work	0.228	2,993	0.003	accepted
Perceived Organizational Support -> Employee Engagement	0.054	0.369	0.712	rejected
Work-Life Balance -> Employee Engagement	0.206	2,257	0.024	accepted
Satisfaction Work -> Employee Engagement	0.517	3,542	0.000	accepted
Indirect effect				
Perceived Organizational Support -> Satisfaction Work -> Employee Engagement	0.338	3,187	0.002	accepted
Work-Life Balance -> Satisfaction Work -> Employee Engagement	0.118	2,357	0.019	accepted

TABLE 1. RESULTS OF DIRECT AND INDIRECT INFLUENCE
 SOURCE: RESULTS OF ANALYSIS WITH SMART PLS, 2022

5) Hypothesis 5 – The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Engagement

The t statistic value is 3.542, which is higher than the t table value of 1.980 based on table 1, and the P-value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05 based on table 1. According to this, Ha

is approved because the Job Satisfaction variable has a favorable and substantial impact on employee engagement. The job satisfaction variable has a positive and significant effect on employee engagement of 51.7%, according to the path coefficient value of 0.517. Because t statistic > t table or P-

values < 0.05 , the study's H5, which claims that "Job satisfaction has a positive and substantial effect on employee engagement," is accepted.

6) Hypothesis 6 – The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Employee Engagement through Job Satisfaction

According to table 1, the t-statistic value is 3.187, which is higher than the t-table value of 1.980, and the P-values are 0.002 and 0.05, respectively. H_0 is accepted because the perceived organizational support variable positively impacts employee engagement measured by job satisfaction. According to the path coefficient value of 0.338, perceived administrative support corporate and considerable influence of 33.8% on employee engagement as measured by work satisfaction. Because the t statistic is greater than the t table or the P-values are less than 0.05, the study's hypothesis, H6, asserts that "Perceived organizational support has a positive and substantial effect on employee engagement through work satisfaction" is accepted.

Regarding employee engagement, this indirect effect has a higher impact than the direct impact of perceived corporate support. It can be said that the mediator's product is perfect and strengthens the relationship between perceived organizational support and employee engagement because the direct relationship between perceived corporate sponsorship and employee engagement, which did not influence first, now has a positive and significant effect.

7) Hypothesis 7 – Effect of Work-Life Balance on Employee Engagement Through Job Satisfaction

Based on table 1, the t statistic value is 2.357, which is greater than the t table, which is 1.980, and the P-values = 0.019, which is less than 0.05. This states that H_0 is accepted because the work-life balance variable positively and significantly affects employee engagement through job satisfaction. The path coefficient value is 0.118, which means that the work-life balance variable has a positive and significant effect on employee engagement through job satisfaction of 11.8%. Thus H7 in this study which states that "Work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on employee engagement through job satisfaction," is accepted because t statistic $>$ t table or P-values $<$ 0.05.

It can be said that the effect the mediation provided was partial because the indirect effect's value is less than the direct effect's value of work-life balance on employee engagement, which is equal to 20.6%, and the direct relationship between work-life balance and employee engagement, which nonetheless has an impact despite the addition of a mediator.

C. Discussion

1) The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Job Satisfaction

The H1 hypothesis is confirmed by empirical evidence and previous research, and the findings indicate that perceived organizational support has a favorable and significant impact on job satisfaction, meaning that one approach is to improve

employee job satisfaction in a company and apply perceived corporate support/good company (POS).

This study's results align with the research showing a strong correlation between job satisfaction and perceived organizational support [26]. The same findings study revealed that perceived company support considerably and positively impacted job satisfaction [27].

The managerial implication of perceived organizational support in PT Rekayasa Industri to help the welfare of its employees is to provide opportunities to continue their studies. The RIR management and division also opens registration for Masters/S3 scholarships for employees who meet several requirements. In addition to the scholarship program, management and the RIR division often hold competitions to raise employee morale and give appreciation through prizes such as shopping vouchers or electronic money to increase employee satisfaction with their work.

2) Effect of Work-Life Balance on Job Satisfaction

The H2 hypothesis is supported by actual evidence and past research, hence it may be said that it is accepted, with the results showing that Job satisfaction is positively and significantly influenced by work-life balance; therefore, improving employee job satisfaction in a firm is one approach in a company is to apply a balance between work and good personal life (WLB).

This study's results align with the research stating that work-life balance significantly affects job satisfaction [13]. A better work-life balance will increase job satisfaction. The same thing from another study said that there was a positive impact between work-life balance and job satisfaction [28].

Managerial implications of work-life balance on job satisfaction in PT Rekayasa Industri in supporting work roles and employee-family relationships, namely by carrying out a working system "Work From Anywhere" or WFA, which means that each employee is not required to work directly in the HO of PT Rekayasa Industri and freed to work from anywhere as long as it does not interfere with the work that has been assigned. Apart from that, the PT Rekayasa Industri HO office also rang a bell indicating that it was 5 pm, allowing all employees to go home immediately and spend time with their families.

3) The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Employee Engagement

The conclusion that hypothesis H3 is rejected implies that more excellent perceived organizational support (POS) has no impact on employee engagement, can be drawn from empirical data, and is supported by prior research.

This study's results differ from research stating that Employee engagement is significantly influenced favorably by perceived organizational support [7], [8]. However, this research aligns with a study that states employee engagement is not significantly positively impacted by perceived organizational support. [9].

Managerial implications related to perceived organizational support do not directly affect employee engagement at PT ReKayasa Industri due to the opposing interests and goals of both employees and management. Employees feel the company must listen to all complaints and take meaningful action. In addition, employees still think that management only makes promises that never materialize, such as an increase in job grade, originally promised every two years. However, many employees who have worked for more than five years are still in the same job grade position. This makes employees feel that the company does not support career paths and reduces feelings of engagement with the company, ultimately making employees think that they will get a better career path at another company.

These complaints must be evaluated by management and the RIR division as a forum for the HR field of PT ReKayasa Industri to be able to listen and respond more to complaints and complaints from employees so that they feel heard and increase their sense of engagement with the company.

4) *Effect of Work-Life Balance on Employee Engagement*

The H4 hypothesis is supported by actual evidence and past research, hence it may be said that it is accepted, with the results showing that employee engagement is positively and significantly impacted by work-life balance, it implies that applying a balance is one strategy to raise employee engagement in a company between jobs with a beautiful personal life (WLB).

This study's results align with previous research which stated that the work-life balance variable has a positive relationship with employee engagement [29]. Research supporting the findings of this study also shows that employee engagement is directly, significantly, and favorably impacted by work-life balance [11].

The managerial implications of work-life balance at PT ReKayasa Industri are related to employee engagement in supporting work roles and employee family relationships, namely by holding family gathering events. Before the pandemic, companies and employees often had outings or family gatherings in large groups or each division which helped build solidarity between companies and employees and their family relationships. By re-holding this family gathering or outing event, it is hoped to create a better work environment and family life and increase employees' sense of engagement with the company.

5) *The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Engagement*

The results demonstrate that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee engagement, indicating that one way to increase employee engagement in a company is to implement job satisfaction. Based on empirical evidence and research from the past, it can be concluded that hypothesis H5 is accepted.

This study's results align with previous research showing that 80% of the variance in employee engagement can be significantly influenced by job satisfaction [30]. Some

researchers also proves that job satisfaction positively and substantially affects employee engagement [31].

Managerial implications of job satisfaction at PT ReKayasa Industri affect increasing satisfaction with the suitability of work with the abilities that employees have are good enough and must be maintained. The leaders have provided portions and work roles that are by the capabilities and background of the employees so that they have the potential to increase employees' sense of engagement with the company.

6) *The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Employee Engagement Mediated by Job Satisfaction*

It is possible to infer that hypothesis H6 is accepted based on empirical evidence and research from the past. The study's findings demonstrate that perceived organizational support positively and significantly influences employee engagement through job satisfaction.

The findings of this study are corroborated by several other studies that found that employee engagement is considerably and favorably influenced by perceived organizational support as measured by job satisfaction [32].

7) *Effect of Work-Life Balance on Employee Engagement Mediated by Job Satisfaction*

It is possible to infer that hypothesis H7 is accepted based on empirical evidence and research from the past. The study's findings demonstrate that work-life balance has a favorable and significant impact on employee engagement as measured by job satisfaction.

The findings of this study are corroborated by several earlier investigations, which found that the work-life balance variable significantly improved job satisfaction [21]. Then, according to research, employee engagement is positively and greatly influenced by work satisfaction [33]. This finding is supported by studies showing that employee job satisfaction significantly and favorably impacts employee engagement.

III. CONCLUSION

The conclusions that can be drawn from this study are as follows.

1. Perceived organizational support has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at PT ReKayasa Industri, with the most dominant indicator, namely, the company is very concerned about employee welfare.
2. Work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at PT ReKayasa Industri, with the most dominant indicator, namely, employees getting support between work and family roles.
3. Perceived organizational support has no positive and significant effect on employee engagement at PT ReKayasa Industri, with the least dominant indicator, namely, the company pays attention to all employee complaints.
4. Work-life balance positively and significantly affects employee engagement at PT ReKayasa Industri. The results show that the direct impact of work-life balance on

- employee engagement has a more excellent value than the indirect effect of work-life balance on employee engagement through job satisfaction.
5. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee engagement at PT Rekayasa Industri with the most dominant indicator, namely, employees feel satisfied with the work given with their abilities
 6. Perceived organizational support positively and significantly affects employee engagement through job satisfaction at PT Rekayasa Industri. Perceived corporate support directly impacts employee engagement more minor than perceived administrative support's indirect effect on employee engagement.
 7. Work-life balance positively and significantly affects employee engagement through job satisfaction at PT Rekayasa Industri. This shows that job satisfaction plays a role in mediating, which means that perceived organizational support and work-life balance will have a higher effect if employees already feel satisfied at work which will increase the employee's sense of engagement at PT Rekayasa Industri.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Khtatbeh M., Mahomed A., Rahman S., & Mohamed, R. "The Mediating Role of Procedural Justice on The Relationship Between Job Analysis and Employee Performance in Jordan Industrial Estates." *Heliyon*, vol 6 no 10, pp 1-9, 2020.
- [2]. Pitasari, N. A., & Perdhana, M. S. "Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan: Studi Literatur." *Diponegoro Journal of Management*, vol 7 no 4, pp 1-11, 2018.
- [3]. Sun, L. "Perceived Organizational Support: A Literature Review." *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, vol 9 no. 3, pp 155-175, 2019.
- [4]. Alkasim, M. A., & Prahara, S. A. "Perceived Organizational Support dengan Employee Engagement Pada Karyawan." *Psikoslamedia Jurnal Psikologi*, vol. 4 no. 2, pp 185-194, 2019.
- [5]. Jaharuddin, N., & Zainol, L. "The Impact of Work-Life Balance on Job Engagement and Turnover Intention". *The South Asian Journal of Management*, pp 106-118, 2019.
- [6]. Wijaya, P., & Edwina, T. "Pengaruh Work Life Balance dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Work Engagement Karyawan." *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Fakultas Pendidikan Psikologi Universitas Negeri Malang*, pp 243-250, 2021.
- [7]. Atmaja, J. W. Pengaruh "Perceived Organizational Support Terhadap Employee Performance Melalui Employee Engagement CV Sumo Surya Perkasa di Lombok." *Jurnal AGORA*, vol 7, no 1, 2019.
- [8]. Sari, M. W., Harahap, E. H., & Sari, V. N. Pengaruh Karakteristik Perceived Organization Support (POS), dan Keadilan Organisasi Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) dengan Employee Engagement Sebagai Variabel Mediasi. *Jurnal ASET (Akuntansi Riset)*, vol 11, no 2, pp 215-223, 2019.
- [9]. Wahyuni, R. A. "Perceived Organizational Support dan Talent Management Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Melalui Employee Engagement." *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*, vol 7, no 4, pp 905-913, 2019.
- [10]. Nurcahyo, T. W. "Reward, Perceived Organizational and Supervisor Support (POS), Work Life Balance Sebagai Faktor Kinerja Karyawan Melalui Employee Engagement." *Jurnal Performance*, vol. 28 no. 2, pp 14-27, 2021.
- [11]. Witriaryani, A. S., Putri, A., Jonathan, D., & Khairal, T. M. "Pengaruh Work-life Balance dan Flexible Working Arrangement Terhadap Job Performance dengan Dimediasi oleh Employee Engagement." *Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi dan Keuangan*, vol. 5 no. 2, pp 932-947, 2022
- [12]. Aryateja, K. B., Susita, D., & Sebayang, K. D. "The Influence of Work-Life Balance and Work Environment on Employee Commitment." *The International Journal of Social Science World*, Vol. 3 No. 2, pp 152-168, 2021.
- [13]. Saptono, N., Supriyadi, E., & Tabroni. Pengaruh *Work Life Balance* dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Melalui *Employee Engagement* Dengan Kesehatan Mental Sebagai Variabel Moderator Pada Karyawan Generasi Milenial." *Jurnal Ekobisman*, vol. 5 no. 2, pp 88-108, 2020.
- [14]. Purnama, A. "Pengaruh Persepsi Pengembangan Karir dan Dukungan Organisasi Terhadap Komitmen Organisasi." *Jurnal Psikoborneo*, vol. 8 no. 2, pp 316-328, 2020.
- [15]. Marfuatun, & Muafi. "Perceived Organizational Support and Psychological Empowerment on Service Performance Mediated by Organizational Citizenship Behaviour Islamic Perspective (OCBIP)." *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, vol 10 no 1, pp 15-27, 2021.
- [16]. Subooh, Y. "A Comparative Study of Work-life Balance and Job Satisfaction of the Employees Working in Business Process Outsourcing Sector." *IRA-International Journal of Management & Social Sciences*, vol 10 no 2, pp 87-93, 2018.
- [17]. Koubova, V. "Life-work Balance: Emotional Intelligence as a Crucial Component of Achieving Both Personal Life and Work Performance." *Management Research Review*, pp 700-719, 2018.
- [18]. Kumara, J., & Fasana, S. "Work Life Conflict and Its Impact on Turnover Intention of Employees: The Mediation Role of Job Satisfaction." *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, vol 8 no 4, 2018.
- [19]. Sutrisno, E. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Kencana, 2019.
- [20]. Widodo, T. W. "Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Bagian Perbendaharaan dan Mobilisasi Dana RSUP Dr. Sardjito." *Jurnal Ekobis Dewantara*, vol. 1 no. 9, pp 118-128, 2018.
- [21]. Rondonuwu, F., Rumawas, W., & Asaloei, S. "Pengaruh Work-Life Balance Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan pada Hotel Sintesa Peninsula Manado." *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis Bol*, vol 7 no 2, pp 30-38, 2018.

- [22]. Pio, R., & Tampi, E. "The Influence of Spiritual Leadership on Quality of Work Life, Job Satisfaction and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour." *International Journal of Law and Management*, vol. 60 no. 2, pp 757-767, 2018.
- [23]. Rinaldy, A. "Pengaruh Employee Engagement, Budaya Organisasi, dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Divisi Line Maintenance PT. Batam Aero Teknik Jakarta." *JIMEN Jurnal Inovatif Mahasiswa Manajemen*, vol 1 no 2, pp 103-112, 2021.
- [24]. Pangestu, T. T., & Wahjuadi, D. "Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Employee Engagement di PT Asuransi Kredit Indonesia (Persero) Cabang Bandung." *Almana: Jurnal Manajemen dan Bisnis*, vol. 3 no. 1, pp 200-216, 2019.
- [25]. Avianto, B., Derriawan, & Tabroni. "Pengaruh Praktik Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia dan Persepsi Dukungan Organisasi Terhadap Keterikatan Karyawan dengan Kualitas Kehidupan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening." *Jurnal Ekonomi Bisnis Manajemen*, vol. 4 no. 2, pp 140-164, 2019.
- [26]. Maan, A. T., Abid, G., Butt, T. H., Ashfaq, F., & Ahmed, S. "Perceived Organizational Support and Job Satisfaction: A Moderated Mediation Model of Proactive Personality and Psychological Empowerment." *Future Business Journal*, pp 1-12, 2020.
- [27]. Lubis, F., & Nurhayati, M. "The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support and Workload on Job Satisfaction Through Work-School Conflict as a Mediating Variable." *Dinasti International Journal of Management Science*, vol. 1 no. 3, pp 277-293, 2020.
- [28]. Suwarli, M., & Sudibjo, N. "Job Embeddeness and Job Satisfaction as a Mediator Between Work-Life Balance and Intention to Stay." *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, vol. 11, no. 8, pp 311-331, 2020.
- [29]. Widayawati, W., Manggabarani, A., & Marzuki, F. "Analisis Pengaruh Kompensasi, Work Life Balance, Kesempatan Berkembang Terhadap Employee Engagement Gen Y PT "X"." *Jurnal Sosial dan Budaya Syari*, Vol. 8 No. 5, pp 1421-1434, 2021.
- [30]. Tepayakul, R. & Rinthaisong, I. "Job Satisfaction and Employee Engagement among Human Resources Staff of Thai Private Higher Education Institutions." *The Journal of Behaviour Science*, vol. 13, no 2, pp 68-81, 2018.
- [31]. Febrial, E., & Hermaningsih, A. "The Effect of Organizational Communication and Job Satisfaction on Employee Engagement and Employee Performance at PT. Abyor International." *Dinasti International Journal of Education Management and Social Science*, vol. 1 issue 4, pp 479-489, 2020
- [32]. Aryanti, S. D., & Herawati, J. "Strategi Meningkatkan Keterlibatan Kerja Karyawan dengan Persepsi Dukungan Perusahaan dan Kompensasi: Kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Intervening pada Karyawan Dinas Tenaga Kerja dan Transmigrasi Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta (DIY)." *Jurnal Ilmiah MEA*, vol. 5 no. 1, pp 47-62, 2021.
- [33]. Pongton, P., & Suntrayuth, S. "Communication Satisfaction, Employee Engagement, Job Satisfaction, and Job Performance in Higher Education Institutions." *ABAC Journal*, vol. 39 no. 3, pp 90-110, 2019.